

PSYCHOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF ATHLETES –
SPRINTERS

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Annotation: The article substantiates the need for psychological preparation of track and field athletes - sprinters. The role of an athlete's psychological preparedness in modern conditions has been determined. A technique aimed at increasing psychological preparedness is described. Exercises are proposed to identify psychological stability immediately before the start.

Key words: Track and field athletes - sprinters, psychological preparation, autogenic training.

Introduction. Recently, in modern sports and psychological-pedagogical science, the issue of setting educational goals in the joint activities of a coach and athletes has become particularly relevant [1, 3]. According to the provisions of a large number of psychological and pedagogical concepts, it is believed that the key subject of educational activity is the athlete [2, 4, 5]. However, the problem of setting goals for its activities is practically not analyzed and is covered only indirectly in the scientific literature. This fact does not allow effective management of the learning process, and also prevents full-fledged joint interaction between the coach and the athlete [3, 6, 8].

Nevertheless, the concept of “goal” is one of the central ones in psychological science, and is considered as a conscious, expressed in words, anticipation of the future result of an action, which is associated with the motive of the activity.

Y. M. Abdullaev considers a goal as an idea of the main result or event that should happen in life, integrating all particular events and justifying human existence [9, 11, 12]. In activity, a goal is set that is in the future, and through thinking, a forecast of the future is carried out. Goals that accumulate personal motivation, organize volitional efforts taking into account social requirements, norms and value orientations, and the ideals of the individual themselves are a manifestation of the most complex work of consciousness [10, 13].

J. Nyttén proved the relationship between the need to achieve a goal and the activity of the individual, which increases the reality of its achievement, while inaction increases the psychological distance to the target object. The author writes that “on the one hand, goals are a specification of behavioral needs, and on the other, goals become self-constructed criteria, standards or norms that must be followed in order for the individual to be satisfied with himself.”

Strategic and global goals of education are dictated by the requirements of society and the state; global goals are guidelines for human activity [15, 18]. However, local goals that are related to a specific activity or learning a specific technique should be more narrow and measurable. Such goals can only be formulated by a coach and an athlete [14, 16, 17].

In practice, it often happens that the goals set by the coach are vague and do not have a sufficient degree of certainty. Traditionally, during classes a global goal is set, that is, a goal that cannot be achieved in one training session. As a result, there is a misunderstanding of these goals by both the coach and, to a greater extent, the athlete.

The main role in the training process of track and field athletes - sprinters is usually given to speed and strength work, but as numerous studies show, without the proper level of psychological preparedness it is impossible to reach heights and demonstrate the desired result [19].

Since 2010, an athlete (sprinter) who has committed one false start is subject to disqualification, while previously (before 2010) they were suspended from participation for a second false start, regardless of who committed the first. Of course, this fact puts serious psychological pressure on the athlete, especially when it comes to important competitions for which he has been preparing, perhaps, his entire career.

The role of psychological preparation is increasing in modern conditions also due to the fact that domestic athletics is now going through a very difficult period. Some federations are suspended from participation in international competitions; athletes have the right to compete only under a neutral flag (and there are not many such athletes). But even in order to obtain neutral status, it is necessary to pass many tests, both legal and moral.

The trend of assigning neutral statuses leads to the fact that young athletes (young men, juniors) are less and less able to achieve it. Consequently, in 8-10 years, when the current high-class athletes of our country finish their sports careers, they will be replaced by a generation that has not participated in international competitions, and therefore does not have the proper experience. In such conditions, the only way to prepare for new competition conditions is to focus on psychological preparation.

If we talk about young and young athletes (12 - 18 years old), then for many of them it is important to show a high result in order to be awarded categories, to take a prize at regional and regional sports competitions. Expectations from the coach and management, especially if these expectations are constantly reinforced by the formulations “you must,” undoubtedly only destroy the psychological mood. All this only proves the need for constant work on psychological preparation.

As part of our research, to increase the level of psychological preparedness of track and field sprinters, we decided to use autogenic training developed by I. Schultz. It is based on the use of muscle relaxation, self-hypnosis and autodidactics

and is a set of exercises aimed at restoring the dynamic balance of the homeostatic mechanisms of the human body, disturbed as a result of stress.

As a result of regular use of this technique in the training process of sprinters, we observed positive changes in both the level of mental preparedness and the growth of sports results. In addition, there was an increase in motivation to achieve high results. Also, after 6 months of regular use of I. Schultz's technique, exercises were carried out aimed at identifying psychological stability immediately before the start.

Athletes were asked to perform a start (from the blocks) under certain conditions. In the first case, the command to start running (let's call it "march!") was given with a slight delay after the command "attention." Under such conditions, the athlete accumulates both psychological and physical stress, which together leads to a premature departure from the blocks (false start).

In the second case, the command to start running was given after a complete false start, that is, when the athlete had previously made a mistake by starting earlier than necessary. In such conditions, as a rule, the psychological state of the athlete is also very tense, as the realization comes that there is no longer any room for error. Awareness of this only heats up the situation and causes additional tension.

Based on the results of these exercises, we came to the conclusion that the participants in the experimental group coped with the task more successfully. The incidence of false starts in this subgroup was 78% lower than in the control group. An analysis of the subjective assessment of the athletes themselves showed that sprinters are more psychologically prepared for the start. Most of them are confident that they are able to contain their pre-race anxiety. In addition, more than half of the study participants noted that another person's false start did not affect their internal tension.

Conclusions. Based on the above, we conclude that the use of autogenic training in the training process significantly increases both the psychological

preparedness of the athlete and objective indicators expressed in the growth of sports results.

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